

WAYS OF DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE AND SPEECH COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article highlights the issues of the development of communicative and speech competence of a teacher in the system of continuing education, gives the concepts of professional competence and competence-based approach to learning. According to the author, every teacher should have clear ideas about the social role of his profession, interest in the child as an object of activity, be able to understand his needs and age characteristics, possess pedagogical observation, pedagogy of cooperation and tact, organizational abilities, have stable spiritual, cognitive interests, be honest, principled, modest, sociable and he must clearly understand that communicative, speech, and information competencies are one of the important components of a specialist's professional competence.*

Russian language teacher should: comprehensively know his subject, understand the role of language as a foreign language in the life of society, know the theory of general linguistics, the theory of speech, all branches of the theory of the Russian language, be philologically educated, constantly monitor the novelties of science and literature in his field, cultural life To own culture speech: to have the skills of free expression of one's thoughts in oral and written forms, to master the language norm (orthoepy, spelling, vocabulary, grammar, etc.), expressive reading, intonation. Possess all the skills and abilities that are mandatory for students at a high level.

Keywords: *communicative and speech, professional competence, tendency, factors, state educational standard, humanization, competence approach, speech culture, the role of language, expressive reading, orthoepy, spelling, vocabulary, grammar, branches of the theory of the Russian language, skills and abilities.*

Introduction

In the modern system of continuous education in Uzbekistan, there have been many positive trends: there is a variability of pedagogical approaches to learning, both for preschoolers and for younger, older schoolchildren and university students; teachers have the freedom for creative search, author's, specialized boarding schools, Presidential schools, private specialized schools are being created, a network of branches of joint universities in different countries is growing; foreign advanced experience is actively and effectively introduced into the system of continuous education of our country; parents are given the opportunity to choose the pedagogical system. At the same time, in my opinion, at present, the theory and practice of the system of lifelong education wants to be much better in scientific, methodological and practical terms, and as for theory, active forms and methods of teaching and upbringing in a general education school are not sufficiently described, and also less used in the teaching process in the field.

Object of study and methods used

The current stage of development of the methodology of teaching school subjects characterizes new approaches to determining the goals and objectives of education. The concepts of “competence”, professional competence and competence-based approach are increasingly included in our lexicon.

The new version of the state educational standard for the Russian language for grades 2-11 of schools with Uzbek and other languages of instruction and the "Concept of teaching Russian as a foreign language" defines three main tasks for teaching Russian as a foreign language: this is the formation of speech (linguistic), communicative and linguistic competencies that contribute to the implementation of the new “Concept for the development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” (No. UP-5712 dated April 29, 2019), developed in pursuance of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures to improve the management system public education” (No. UP-5538 of September 5, 2018).

In accordance with this, humanization, democratization, informatization of education are considered as key positions for updating the teaching of Russian as a foreign language, as factors for accelerating the development of the school - the teacher's creative search, the dynamism of the educational process, its multivariance, focus not only on the perception and improvement of social experience, but also on its cardinal transformation and development as value priorities that determine the content of education.

Before talking about competence, professional competence and competence approach in teaching, it is necessary to define these concepts.

The formation of the teacher's professional competence (this includes communicative-speech, informational competence, etc.) is today one of the main tasks of the modern system of lifelong education. The concept of professional competence should be distinguished from traditional knowledge, skills and abilities.

Professional competence should be understood as an integral characteristic of the business personal qualities of a specialist, reflecting their level of knowledge, skills, experience, sufficient to implement a certain type of activity. The formed communicative-speech and information competences are an important indicator of the teacher's professional competence. Only then can the quality and efficiency of the educational process be achieved if professionally competent teachers are involved in the training.

What is the professional competence of a teacher?

1. Extensive and deep knowledge in the field of the science taught;
2. Perfectly mastering the methodology of teaching the subject and ICT;
3. Armed with knowledge from pedagogy, general and developmental psychology, the ability to use them in the practice of training and education;
4. General high culture and erudition;
5. Formed communicative-speech, information and other competencies.

The professional competence of a modern teacher should be considered as a multifactorial phenomenon, as a culturological component of professionalism, as a holistic competence-based education, which includes a system of theoretical and practical knowledge of a teacher and methods of their application in specific pedagogical situations, value orientations, as well as integrative indicators of his culture (speech, style of communication or communication, attitude towards oneself and one's activity, informativeness, etc.).

What is included in the professional skills of a modern teacher?

Each teacher must have a clear understanding of the social role of his profession, interest in the child as an object of activity, be able to understand his needs and age characteristics, possess pedagogical observation, pedagogy of cooperation and tact, organizational skills, have sustainable spiritual, cognitive interests, be honest, principled, modest, sociable. If we are talking about a teacher of the Russian language, then he must: comprehensively know his subject, understand the role of a language as a foreign language in the life of society, know the theory of general linguistics, the theory of speech, all branches of the theory of the Russian language, be philologically educated, constantly monitor the latest in science and literature in their field, for cultural life. Possess a culture of speech: have the skills to freely express one's thoughts in oral and written forms, own the language norm (orthoepy, spelling, vocabulary, grammar, etc.), expressive reading, intonations. To master at a high level all those skills and abilities that are required for students.

Competence (from Latin *competentia*. This is a range of issues in which someone has good knowledge, experience and awareness) can be objectively observed, measurable with a certain accuracy, purposefully formed.

Competence is a consequence of learning, as it relates to the individual, and is formed in the process of performing a certain set of actions. If professional pedagogical activity is considered as a solution to certain problems, then this approach involves the development of the following key competencies: recognition of practical problems, their formulation, translation of problems into the form of a task, correlation with the context of the obtained knowledge system, analysis and evaluation of the result.

Many scientists have come to the conclusion that competence is such a quality of a person that exists and develops in a dual unity: in a person and society. Thus, by developing competence, we develop the personal qualities of the subject and the qualities that connect him with society, with life. In modern scientific literature, there are several definitions of the concepts of "competence" and professional competence. The definition given by the scientist Elkonin can be considered closest and more specific: "Competence is a measure of a person's involvement in activities."

It should be said that competence is a personal quality of a specialist, prone to development and improvement. This is what creates a vast field of activity for the modern teacher. It is the teachers of the Russian language and literature who are, of course, the key figure in modern student-centered education, in the formation of all types of key competencies, especially communicative-speech, linguistic, informational, etc.

Today, for the successful self-realization of their knowledge, skills and abilities, a modern teacher needs three key components: creativity, wide mastery of information and communication technologies, the formation of communicative speech and information competencies. Particular attention should be paid to communicative and speech competence, which comes first before linguistic, linguistic, informational and cultural studies and is one of the components of professional competence.

Communicative and speech competence should be understood as "mastery of all types of speech activity (speaking, reading, writing, listening) and the basics of the culture of oral and written speech, basic skills and abilities to use the language in vital areas and situations of communication for this age."

The formation of communicative competence involves knowledge of speech, its functions, the development of skills in the field of four main types of speech activity (speaking, listening and understanding, reading, writing).

Communicative competence implies the ability for full speech communication in all spheres of human activity, in compliance with social norms of speech behavior. The main skill formed within the framework of communicative competence is the ability to create and perceive texts - products of speech activity. It includes knowledge of the basic concepts of linguistics of the language - styles of speech, types of speech, the structure of the description, narration, reasoning, ways of connecting sentences in the text, etc., skills and abilities of text analysis.

There are different components of the situation or speech conditions that dictate the speaker's choice of words and grammatical structures. This is, firstly, the relationship between the interlocutors and their social roles. It should be said that the nature of verbal communication will be different depending on who we are communicating with, what is the social status of the speakers: teacher or student, teacher or student, what is their age, gender, interests, etc. Secondly, the place of communication (for example, communication between a teacher and a student in a classroom, a teacher with a student in a lesson, during a break, a teacher with students in a conversation, or a librarian with a reader (student, student) in the library. The third, very important component of speech situations - the goal and intentions of the speaker. So, an order, advice, request or demand, of course, will differ from a message, information or their emotional assessment, an expression of gratitude, joy, resentment, etc.

Thus, the actual communicative competences are the skills and abilities of verbal communication, taking into account who we are talking to, where we are talking, and, finally, for what purpose.

There is no doubt that their formation is possible only on the basis of linguistic and linguistic competencies. The need for training in different competencies is essentially the answer of education to the challenges of modern society, which is characterized by ever-increasing complexity and dynamism.

Therefore, the competency-based approach to teaching focuses not on increasing the amount of a person's awareness in various subject areas, but on helping people solve problems on their own in unfamiliar situations. The same skills that help a person to navigate in new situations of their professional, personal and social life, achieving their goals, began to be called competencies or key competencies.

The competence-based approach puts forward in the first place not the student's awareness, but the skills and abilities to solve problems by analogy that arise in the following situations:

The essence of the competence-based approach to learning is that it is not "ready-made knowledge" proposed by the teacher for assimilation that is assimilated, but "the conditions for the origin of this knowledge are traced". The student himself forms the concepts necessary for solving problems. With this approach, learning activity, periodically acquiring a research character, itself becomes the subject of assimilation. In other words, the competency-based approach suggests that one should teach not just specific "frozen" knowledge, but one should "teach to learn". The main task of the teacher, as K.D. Ushinsky wrote, is to turn the student's activity into amateur activity. And in turn, this depends on the competence-based approach to learning, professional competence (from communicative-speech, language, linguistic and informational competences) of the teacher.

Therefore, modern pedagogical technologies, experimental activities are the reality of the current approach to education and upbringing. The teacher or lecturer needs to understand that now the way of presenting the material and exchanging information is not as important as the way of joint activity, that the learning objectives have changed. And they should be aimed at the formation of key educational competencies in students, which cannot be solved without communicative speech and information competencies.

Today, the position of the teacher is also fundamentally changing. We need to stop being, together with the textbook, the carrier of "objective knowledge" that we are trying to convey to students. Our main task should be to motivate students to show initiative and independence. We must intensify the independent activity of students, in which everyone could realize their abilities and interests. In fact, in this way we create conditions, a developing environment in which it becomes possible for each student to develop certain competencies at the level of development of his intellectual and other abilities, especially communicative-speech and information.

The widespread use of interactive methods and techniques involves "co-education", where both students and the teacher are subjects of the educational process.

Interactive learning allows you to solve several problems at the same time, the main of which is the development of communication skills. This training helps to establish emotional contacts between students, provides an educational task, because it teaches you to work in a team, listen to the opinions of your comrades, provides high motivation, strength of knowledge, creativity and imagination, sociability, an active life position, the value of individuality, freedom of expression, an emphasis on activity, mutual respect and democracy. One of the effective active methods of teaching the Russian language is the introduction of elements of research activities in the classroom and outside the classroom. The practical result of this work is scientific reports - presentations, joint with teachers, scientific articles in journals, collections of materials from scientific and practical conferences, training seminars. It should be noted that doing research activities, for example, in linguistics, is very useful for students of philology. This form of work introduces students to independent analysis of works, individual books, dictionaries, encyclopedias, Internet materials, scientific articles, etc. In addition, this type of activity contributes to the development of independent thinking, cultivates speech culture, develops types of speech activity, broadens horizons, enriches skills scientific approach to linguistic problems. And most importantly, this method forms students' communicative-speech, informational and linguistic competencies.

Thus, the main goal of the competence-based approach in teaching any subject is to form a comprehensively developed personality of a schoolchild (student), his independent thinking, linguistic intuition and abilities, mastering the culture of communicative speech communication and behavior.

Communicative orientation - mastery of modern means of communication, the formation of skills and abilities to express thoughts in oral and written forms, a characteristic feature of the current curriculum in Russian as a foreign language.

The new curriculum for teaching Russian as a foreign language for schools of general secondary education with Uzbek and other languages of instruction has the following main goals and objectives:

the formation of communicative and speech competence, the development of skills in the use of the Russian language in the process of communication, to continue learning and everyday

life of students; the formation of key general educational competencies aimed at developing students' self-education, as well as the ability to use the acquired skills, knowledge and skills in social life and personal activities; the formation of linguistic competence aimed at the functional mastery of the grammatical system of the Russian language and the development of oral and written speech of students.

Practical mastery of the Russian language for use in the most important areas of communication: everyday, educational, socio-political, socio-cultural is the main goal of this program.

Each person entering this complex and contradictory world needs certain thinking skills and personality traits. The ability to analyze, compare, highlight the main thing, solve a problem, the ability to improve themselves and the ability to give adequate self-esteem, be responsible, independent, be able to create and cooperate - these are the qualities that modern children should develop. Therefore, the task of each teacher (whatever his specialty) is to build the learning process in such a way as to help the spiritual forces of the child open up. A competent teacher needs not only to tell and show everything in an accessible way, but also to teach the student to speak and think, to instill in him the skills of practical actions. This will largely be helped by interactive forms, methods and techniques of teaching, which contribute to the formation of the communicative and speech competence of the teacher and students, and the development of independent learning activities.

The modern strategy of progress of the advanced countries of the world is based on the concept of comprehensive cultural, intellectual, professional and physical development of the potential of the individual. At the same time, in the implementation of its goals, the main place is given to the system of continuous education. Today, by raising the level of education of the population, the developed countries of the world receive almost half of the gross national product. Therefore, the informatization of education and the competence-based approach to learning in the world in general, and in Uzbekistan in particular, are of great importance.

The main competence of the subject teacher becomes his updated role - the role of a conductor of knowledge, a kind of "navigator" that helps students navigate the boundless sea of information. The use of information technology in the educational process allows not only to modernize it, increase efficiency, motivate students, but also differentiate the process, taking into account the individual characteristics of each student. The relevance of this topic is due to the fact that computers are increasingly invading the humanities and natural areas of education, their skillful use arouses a strong interest among students in the subject, helps them study with enthusiasm, achieve high results in educational activities. The scope of the study is an educational process that contributes to the formation and development of communicative competence and motivation to study subjects with the help of ICT.

Today you can often hear from teachers that in the age of computer technology, the latest TCO and new developments in audio-video technology, it has become quite difficult to get students interested in learning. Especially with Russian. The importance of the English language came to the fore.

What should a teacher do in such a situation? How should he interest students so that they begin to study Russian or other subjects?

First of all, any teacher should increase interest in studying his subject among schoolchildren. If this is a teacher of the Russian language, you need to start simple: you need to

constantly remind students that the Russian language is one of the world languages, it was and remains a communicative means of communication between the peoples inhabiting the former republics that were part of the USSR, and to this day it has not lost the meaning of the "language of interethnic communication" in the CIS countries.

The teacher also needs to be constantly reminded of the Russian language as the language in which world problems are solved at UN meetings, because it is one of the languages spoken by half of the members of the United Nations.

By showing the world and international significance of the language, students can be interested in learning Russian as a foreign language. It will be an interest in another foreign language, which will open up prospects in the future.

This interest should be fixed in the purposeful work of the teacher to improve self-education in the constant use of interactive forms, methods and techniques of teaching in the educational process. To increase interest in their subject, any teacher must master the latest technology in teaching the subject. The purposeful application of innovative technologies in teaching contributes to the formation of communicative and speech competence of both the teacher and students, as well as the development of their mental activity.

Any job requires the development of certain skills. And the most important skill that every highly qualified specialist should have is the skill of self-education.

Self-education is the need of a creative and responsible person in any profession, especially for professions with increased moral and social responsibility, such as the teaching profession.

Self-education of a teacher is a necessary condition for the professional activity of a teacher. Therefore, professional growth can also be called the search for one's own path, finding one's own voice. No wonder Leo Tolstoy said about the teacher: "If the teacher stops working, then the teacher dies in him." These expressions have become winged and have a deep meaning.

Self-education is one of the important factors in the formation of professional competence, communicative-speech, linguistic and informational competences of a teacher.

When creating a model for a program of professional and personal self-development, it is important to proceed from the fact that today society needs initiative and independent specialists who are able to constantly improve their personality and activities. Being engaged in self-education according to a personal self-development plan, one can achieve significant success in work, proving that students develop a new system of knowledge, skills and abilities; pupils' self-activity in their subjects develops, which contributes to an increase in the effectiveness of schoolchildren's education.

What motives encourage self-education?

Daily work with information requires more and more knowledge not only in the search and analysis of new information, but also in its storage, use and reliability.

Desire for creativity. Teaching is a creative profession. A creative teacher should not work from year to year according to the same lesson plan or scenario, read the same reports. Work should be interesting and enjoyable.

Competition. Opportunity to be in demand at work. Today, it is no secret to anyone that many parents, bringing their child to school, ask to be in the class of a particular teacher or class teacher.

Activities in the process of self-education, contributing to the improvement of the professional competence of the teacher.

- Regular viewing of certain TV programs;
- Reading pedagogical periodicals;
- Reading scientific-methodical, pedagogical and fiction literature;
- Acquaintance with Internet materials in their subject, pedagogy, psychology, modern educational technology;
- Attendance at training seminars, master classes, lessons of colleagues, scientific and practical conferences;
- Discussions, meetings, exchange of experience with colleagues;
- Study of modern pedagogical methods in the process of interactive trainings;
- Timely completion of advanced training courses;
- Study of information and computer technologies;
- Visiting subject exhibitions and thematic excursions on the subject;
- Maintaining a healthy lifestyle, playing sports, physical exercises.

Stages of self-education:

The content of the concept of professional competence of a teacher includes three aspects of the qualities and properties of a person:

- professional and personal, associated with the development and development of professional knowledge and skills, intellectual potential and emotional-volitional sphere; - professional and activity-related, associated with the development of the individual and the creation of conditions for its self-development;

- professional and creative, associated with the readiness of the teacher to perceive and implement innovative ideas, new information, the ability to master new technologies.

This approach makes it possible to form a model for the development of professional competence in the conditions of additional pedagogical education as an integral, dynamic system that includes diagnostic, information-motivational, design-organizational and generalizing stages.

conclusions

Thus, from all of the above, we can draw the following conclusion: all these requirements for education are called upon to fulfill a professionally competent teacher. The peculiarity of his work is that the object and product is the most “unique in its value material” - a person. And not just a person, but a growing person, his inner world.

The changes taking place in the life of modern society, first of all, are reflected in the students, form their worldview, and accordingly, I would not like my image to be formed in them as the image of an “outdated person”.

The teacher today must strive to fulfill the basic principles of lifelong education. Keep up with the times and be able to anticipate future requirements.

Improving the quality of training and education in the system of continuous education directly depends on the level of training of the teacher. Society has always provided the teacher with good working conditions and made the highest demands. Now these requirements are increasing exponentially. After all, in order to teach others, you need to know more than everyone else, and be able to transfer this knowledge to others and students. The teacher must not only be proficient in the methodology of teaching the subject, but also be knowledgeable in other fields of knowledge, in various spheres of public life, and be oriented in modern politics and economics. The teacher must learn everything all the time, because, in the faces of his students in front of him, time stages change every year, ideas about the world around him deepen and even change.

Today, a modern school does not need a teacher - a "tutor". Today, all types of educational institutions of the system of continuous education need teachers, teachers who deeply know their subject, modern teaching methods, who own modern ICT and are able to purposefully and effectively use them in the educational process, teach children to acquire knowledge on their own.

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